

EXPOSURE OF ICT IN TEACHING & LEARNING

S. Shrinivasa* & S. M. Ravindra Gouda**

* Physical Education Teacher, Government High School, Singrihalli,
Davanagere, Karnataka

** Assistant Director of Physical Education, Kuvempu University, Karnataka

Cite This Article: S. Shrinivasa & S. M. Ravindra Gouda, "Exposure of ICT in Teaching & Learning", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 52-54, 2018.

Introduction:

The type of communication device is the computer and the process of communication via the computer and its allied components is known as Information and Communication Technology.

Meaning of ICT:

Information Communication Technology (ICT) is the combination of computer, video and telecommunications technologies, as seen in the use of multimedia computers and the networks and services based upon them. The first term is related to technology and the second one is related to "learn through movement". It is important to know the definition of ICT and the use it has for physical education if we are to provide a well founded answer. Information and communication technology has a role in the learning and teaching process as a teaching tool. ICT involves both teachers and students in the learning and facilitation process.

As far as the information technology becomes more widespread, the importance of computer and technology use increases and turns out to be an important element in human resources (Ono and Zavodny, 2004). Both the educators and the public accept the necessity for the students to be competent in computer use. In order to benefit from technology in education, both the teachers and students should have enough knowledge about computers. However the discussions about the limits of computer use in educational activities are still continuing. In many schools computers are used only for internet access and game play. The suitability of computer applications with the curriculum and the applications in classroom is usually overlooked (Moursund, 1995). Physical education teachers can also teach a subject in their curriculum by first analyzing it technically in computer laboratory. By that way they can teach the biomechanics visually and then move on to the application of those techniques which will help for a more productive course.

Quality at all levels of education is the need of today's world. The information expansion which is the outcome the development in the field of ICT has been responsible for changing the outlook of education to a greater extent. In this era of globalization, liberalization and privatization the process of education has become more quality oriented. Especially the increasing private participation in the education process has been the turning point for more utilization of ICT in teaching learning and institutional management. The exposure to digital resources has been extremely useful in updating the information of almost everything.

Use of ICT to Teachers:

- ✓ ICT enable to enhance the initial preparation by giving good teaching and training materials, use simulators according and feed back in teaching.
- ✓ With the help of ICT teachers can access with colleagues, schools, institutions, universities, expertise rich resource at cyber space
- ✓ ICT enable to interact with students over a physical distance.

Use of ICT in Teaching:

Teaching at School as well as Higher Education, mostly, concentrates on giving information which is not the sole objective of Teaching. Along with giving information, the other objectives are:

- ✓ Developing understanding and application of the concepts
- ✓ Developing reasoning and thinking power
- ✓ Development of judgment and decision making ability
- ✓ Developing self-concept and value clarification
- ✓ Developing proper study habits
- ✓ Developing tolerance and ambiguity, risk taking capacity, scientific temper, etc.

With the present infrastructure, class size, availability of teachers, quality of teachers, training of teachers, etc., it is difficult to achieve all the objectives. Further, most of the teachers use Lecture Method which does not have potentiality of achieving majority of above mentioned objectives. The objectives are multi-dimensional in nature, so for their achievement multiple methods should be used in an integrated fashion. At present ICT may be of some use. It is a well-known fact that not a single teacher is capable of giving up to date and complete information in his own subject. The ICT can fill this gap because it can provide access to different sources of information. It will provide correct information as comprehensive as possible in different formats with different examples. ICT provides online interaction facility. Students and teachers can exchange their ideas and views, and get clarification on any topic from different experts, practitioners, etc. It helps learners to broaden the information base. ICT provides variety in the presentation of content which helps learners in

concentration, better understanding, and long retention of information which is not possible otherwise. The learners can get opportunity to work on any live project with learners and experts from other countries. The super highway and cyber space also help in qualitative improvement of Teaching – Learning Process. ICT provides flexibility to learners which are denied by the traditional process and method. Flexibility is a must for mastery learning and quality learning. The world is changing towards a knowledge based economy. It was said that the knowledge improved doubles every two to three years. Every year there were more than 7000 scientific articles published with the research. Today's students of the industrialized nations gain more information rather than their grandparents were exposed to their lifetime. The greatest challenge for society in which we live today is keeping pace with the knowledge technological expertise necessary for finding, applying and evaluating information. This has a special meaning and challenge not only to the educationist but also to the persons who were involved in the system. Information literacy is a survival way in this information age. There is a flood of knowledge through ICT, the information literate people can only survive their lives in such type of floods. The information literate people can analyze, evaluate, use and knows how to search information to overcome their problems. It does not matter the information comes from computer, a book, a government agency or from other possible modern electronic devices. The learners must have the ability to use information and technology effectively. The information exploits every sphere of human activities. There is a saturation of information through new technologies. There is a need of the development of the use of such information and communication technology for the survival. Understanding ICT and mastering the basic skills and concepts were parts and care of education. These Information and Communication Technologies are so far away from the reading and writing habits. ICT can be used arose the curriculum.

ICT has become within a very short time. One of the foundational educational pedagogy for a modern literature society. Nations many now regard the methodological relevance of the ICT additive to the mastery of the pre- requisite basic skills and concept of ICT as an important part of core- fundamentals of education. Besides other educative advantages of reading, writing and numerical skills.

ICT have always cherished and reflected better/ new possibilities into the classroom teaching practices and learning environments. The use of ict can invoke substantial changes for skilled teaching. ICT based resources have been popularized in traditional education system in different forms. Curriculum design of traditional face –to face mode system may insist on the ICT input to be used for attaining specific objectives. Such an approach is known as integrated approach. This involves careful and considered review of the curriculum area and selection of appropriate ICT resources which will contribute to the aim and objectives of the curriculum in different subject areas.

Another approach of using ICT in teaching and learning is called enhancement approach where the teacher may like to use ICT materials as a component of delivery of lessons in classroom situations. The use of ICT resources empowers the learners in enhancement of learning skills. The students make use of various ICT based resources to prepare projects, by submitting assignments through e-mail making library notes, by word processing own home work etc...ICT have emerged as the major determining forces of this century in shaping the global economy and producing rapid change in society.

In recent years, the ICT tools have fundamentally changed the way people communicate and do business. Educational systems around the world are under increasing pressure to use the new information and communication technologies to teach students the knowledge and skills they need in the 21st century.

The 1998 UNESCO, world education report, teachers and teaching in a changing world, describes the radical implications the new informations and communication technologies have for conventional teaching and learning. It predicts the transformation of the teaching learning process and the way teachers and learners gain access to knowledge and information. Technology by itself is not the answer too... educational problems. The power of technology will come from its combination with serious educational reforms.

ICT and Teacher Education:

There are a variety of approaches to professional development of teachers in the context of use of ICT in education. Professional development to incorporate ICT in to teaching and learning is an ongoing process should not be thought of as one injection of training. Teachers need to update their knowledge and skills as the school curriculum and technologies change.

Conclusion:

The ICT has arrived in a big way; there is no escape from it. And why should we try to escape from it, when the whole process of teaching learning improves so dramatically? ICT helps in making the teaching learning process learner centered. Every time the teacher educator interacts, plans new activities for the learners, it is a very rich learning experience for her/him also. Web resources are increasing at a very high speed, so a teacher could develop fresh learning activities every semester as compared to using the same old.

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